

Using citation networks for viewpoint plurality assessment of historical literary corpora: The case of the Medieval Rabbinic corpus

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The digital networking sphere enables analysis of author groups, defining in-group dynamics, and mapping out inter-group relationships (Baumann et al., 2020). While intellectual diversity and inclusiveness is one of the important principles of modern scholarship, it is intriguing to explore the extent to which these principles apply to historical communities of leaders and intellectuals. This paper introduces a novel methodological framework aimed at assessing the degree of viewpoint plurality of historical scholarship communities, through an in-depth analysis of the citations used in their literature, which has become possible due to the recently developed advanced computational analysis techniques (Romanello, 2016; Colavizza, 2017; Rodrigues Alves et al., 2018).

To this end, we developed a set of new network-based indicators based on standard network metrics, such as 1) resource diversity: the number of distinct external resources from other communities in the network out of all the distinct cited resources; and 2) citations' external outdegree: the number of the outgoing citations of other communities' resources out of all the outgoing citations. These indicators are applied both at individual author and community levels.

Through this amalgamation, we aim to tackle queries like: How extensively does an individual or a group harness content from its counterparts? How diverse are their referencing habits? Are there universally accepted resources?

As an implementation of the proposed methodology, we automatically analyzed a large corpus of Rabbinic Halachic literature from 10 to 15 CE and constructed a citation network of authors and books. The network comprises over 750,000 citations extracted and mapped from hundreds of significant books penned by approximately 140 Rabbinic authors who cited over 250 scholars and hundreds of volumes from the early Jewish writings originating from diverse regions such as North Africa, Spain, Provence, Italy & Balkan, France, and Ashkenaz (mostly modern-day Germany) that maintained intellectual ties of various kinds during the period (Ta-Shma, 2000).

The proposed network-based quantitative analysis provides an exploration into the patterns of intellectual exchange, enabling us to trace the multi-directional influences between various rabbinic authors and communities (see Figures 1-3). The figures reveal distinctive citation patterns among different communities. Notably, the French community, characterized by the lowest number of outgoing citations, demonstrates a remarkable emphasis on internal references. Furthermore, it attracts a considerable number of incoming citations from Spain and Ashkenaz. In contrast, the Italian community emerges as particularly open-minded and inclusive, boasting the highest proportion of external outgoing citations, reflecting a willingness to engage with a diverse range of viewpoints.

In summary, even though this is a Medieval literature produced by religious leaders (who as such might be perceived as closed-minded and conservative), we found that most of the authors and communities cite many more external resources from other communities than their own. Although the reasons for the

discovered phenomena could be explored by domain experts, our methodology remains domain agnostic, making it suitable for any sufficiently inclusive and comprehensive corpus.

Figure 1: Authors' plurality based on the integration of the two proposed citation-based indicators – resource diversity and citations' external outdegree.

Figure 2: Cross-community citation heatmap. Cell shading intensity in each row represents the external outdegree scores, i.e. the percentage of the outgoing citations of the different communities by a given community.

Figure 3: Community-level citation network visualization. The size of the nodes is proportional to the number of outgoing citations of the represented community, the thickness of the edges is calculated based on the number of outgoing citations of different communities.

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